

ALKALI-RESISTANT NANO-COATINGS FOR GLASS FIBRES IN A CEMENTITIOUS MATRIX

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SUMMARY: Despite the glass fibre being considered as a reinforcement of cementitious materials for several decades, the structural applications are limited by its poor corrosion resistance in a highly alkaline environment. Here, we describe an inexpensive and applicable process by which a nanometer-scale polymer surface coating layer based on styrene butadiene with varied concentrations, as environmental barrier interphase, was applied to the commercially sized and tailor-made sized alkali-resistant glass fibres (ARG). Our data indicates that the polymer coating designs the glass fibre with significantly improved both corrosion resistance to alkali and fracture energy absorption capability of its composites. Moreover, an assessment of changes in the fibre surface chemical and nanomechanical properties is provided and a strong correlation between the tensile strength, roughness and Griffith fracture predictions is noted. We examine the fracture mechanisms of composites at different scales based on a mechanical-statistical and an geometry analysis.

KEYWORDS: glass fibre, polymer coating, interface, durability, cement matrix composites, atomic force microscopy, nanoindentation.

INTRODUCTION

Previous research results lead to the conclusion that using ARG in textiles with an optimal arrangement of reinforcement fibres in connection with a concrete layer provides new possibilities for retrofitting and structural strengthening [1]. Besides the textile processes, which is a precondition for manufacturing highly-productive multi axial reinforcement structures, the stress transfer from the cementitious matrix to the fibres in the composite is the main issue. The reduced resistance of ARG in the alkaline environment of the cementitious matrix based on Portland cements (pH-value 13-14) leads gradually to a decrease of strength and deformation ability [2,3]. The durability of ARG in cement is affected mainly by two mechanism. First, the ARG is attacked chemically due to the high alkalinity of the binder and second, the mechanical properties degrade because of hydration products, essentially calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) [4,5]. Currently, the mechanisms of adhesion improvement are not known completely. Besides the influence on the composite performance by the cementitious matrix and the alkali-resistant reinforcement fibres, the interactions between both phases in the three-dimensional interphase is also highly important. In contrast to polymer matrix composites, which has very homogeneous impregnation of each single filament and a high adhesion strength, the cementitious matrix has no homogeneous fibre distribution and little impregnation of each fibre because of the textile structure and accessibility by the matrix. In addition, the adhesion strength can be influenced by sizings and further additives that effect the friction. The sizing, which is typically a few tens of nanometer in average thickness, basically consists of components of a organo-silane coupling agent, a polymer film former and a lubricant, leading to variable properties and great difficulty in both process control and in-situ characterization. These additives are responsible for both adhesion strength improvement, protection against alkaline attack, and must also fulfil a mechanical role to

improve the fibre strength. For these reasons fundamental research is done to reveal the mechanisms of adhesion for model cases of differently sized fibres and coated structures [6,7]. In order to evaluate the behaviour of the composites a systematic development of suitable sizings (chemistry, adhesion, formation of the interphase, alkaline resistance, amount of organic substances) is necessary. High importance for the influence on composites formation is attributed to the application of interphase active substances. For the modelling of the sizing in the case of aggregates of reinforcing fibres, both the adhesion strength of each single filament and the stress transfer to adjacent filaments has to be considered.

At first, the experiments were carried out by application of polymer coatings on commercial ARG roving surfaces [8]. Because the constituents of commercial sizings are unknown, an adjusted development of compatible polymer coatings was impossible. A selected sizing formulation was successfully used for ARG manufactured by the company, Nippon Electric Glass (NEG). However, the composites showed significantly lower adhesion strength and fracture energies than the composite with ARG supplied by Vetrotex International (VET). After completion of the technological equipment and analysis of the model cases, ARG is spun at the Leibniz Institute of Polymer Research Dresden and fibre surface is modified. The mechanical properties of coatings must be adequate to guarantee mechanical stability and integrity for their period of use. To the best of our knowledge, to date experimental information obtained with the use of an AFM nanoindentation for fibre surface was rarely reported in literature. One of the major problems with glass fibres is that the measured tensile strength is significantly lower than its theoretical value. This is evidently due to preexisting defects which show multiple populations with varying gauge length [9]. The surface flaws providing extra stress at the tip of the cracks can lead to stress-corrosion cracking at very low stress level. Surface coating is believed efficiently to protect the fibre surface against moisture attack and improve its mechanical properties through a three-dimensional graded network on the glass surface [10]. This “healing” effect was viewed as a disappearance of the severe surface flaws because of an increase of the crack tip radius, the flaw filled by coating being either elliptical than sharp [9].

The major objective of this work is to investigate the effect of the organic coatings applied on the ARG fibre surfaces before and after exposure to concentrated alkaline environmental attacks. We study both the surface and interphase properties in terms of surface stiffness, morphology, chemical composition and adhesion. A combination of nanoindentation, AFM, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy by attenuated total reflectance (FTIR-ATR) and Zetapotential measurements is used. For the simulation of the effectiveness of fibre surface coatings, the results of fibre bundle pull-out tests are considered and Griffith fracture predictions are correlated with surface roughness variability. Special emphasis is placed on a Weibull statistical equation to describe the fracture behavior of fibre bundles embedded in cements. Besides, it is also tempting to correlate the fracture surface morphology of pulled-out single fibres to microscopic mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material and methods of investigation

In this work ARG supplied by Nippon Electric Glass Co Ltd. (NEG-ARG) and Cem-FIL Vetrotex International (VET-ARG) were investigated and compared with those spun at IPF (IPF-ARG). On the one hand, a polymer coating was applied to enhance the adhesion within the roving and with the cementitious matrix [8]. The coated fibres, namely C1 and C2, have coating contents of 2.4 and 7 wt %, and the calculated average sizing thickness values are about 100 nm and 270 nm, respectively.

In order to evaluate the failure behaviour of composites single fibre pull-out tests, roving pull-out tests, and longitudinal tensile tests of concrete specimens with roving reinforcements were carried out [7]. For performing the roving pull-out test the ARG and hybrid samples were

embedded in a cementitious matrix at a constant embedding length of 10 mm. This length has been determined in previous trials and leads predominantly to adhesive failure. The specimens were cured at ambient temperature in humid environment (>90% RH) for 28 days and were tested to determine the maximum roving pull-out force F_{max} using an universal testing machine with a constant crosshead-speed of 1 mm/min and a free fibre length close to zero. The fracture surface was examined using a scanning electron microscope (LEO 435VP).

For the tensile tests, rectangular composite specimens were made with three rovings embedded in the cementitious matrix along the centre line in longitudinal direction. A concrete breaking point was predetermined in the middle of the specimen. The first part of the force-displacement curve shows the failure behaviour of the concrete, whereas the second part represents the fracture energy, given by the sum of the energy contributions of (i) interfacial adhesion, (ii) filament failure and (iii) friction between roving and concrete matrix during fibre pull-out. The force maximum of this part reflects an apparent fracture energy.

To predict the long-term behaviour of ARG fibres in concrete in a short term, recently, we have employed accelerated aging methods that entail raising alkalinity and temperature of the test environment aging [6]. Here, we only extracted the above three kinds of fibres in a selected highly concentrated alkaline aqueous solution (5 wt % NaOH at 23 °C for 28 days, pH of 13), which is the most aggressive and corrosive condition to the fibre surface out of the tested ones under ambient temperature.

The single fibre tensile measurement was conducted under 65 % RH and 20°C using the Fafegraph ME testing device (Fa. Textechno) equipped with a 10 N force cell. The test cross velocity is 10 mm/min and the gauge length is 20 mm in accordance with EN ISO 5079. Based on a vibration approach, the fineness of each selected fibre was determined by using a Vibromat ME (Fa. Textechno) in accordance with EN ISO 53812 and ASTM D 1577.

In order to gain insight into what mechanisms are responsible for tensile strength variation after exposure to various environmental attacks, investigation of the surface morphology, chemical composition and mechanical elastic/plastic property of the ARG fibre was conducted. An AFM (a Digital Instruments D3100, USA) was used as both a surface imaging tool and a nanoindentation device to evaluate the fibre and surface properties. The topography of samples was studied in tapping mode. The cantilever (ULTRASHARP NSC16/50, MikroMasch, Estonia) has a normal spring constant of 35 N/m, a tip cone angle of 20 °, radius of 5~10 nm and modulus of 160 GPa to assure good imaging resolution and nanometer scale indents. The mechanical properties of a thin layer on fibre surface were determined by the nanoindentation, which allow precise continuous and simultaneous measurements of the load F and penetration depth h , with a displacement resolution of 0.16 nm. The measurements were made in the normal load range from 0.01~1 μ N and indentation depth range from 0.2 - 20 nm. Specimens were prepared by fixing separate short fibre filaments on a steel plate, within a thin layer of pre-coated epoxy at the bottom side of the fibre.

Roughness parameters derived from ASME B46.1 (the American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Surface Roughness, Waviness and Lay) are calculated based upon the following definitions. Image mean roughness (R_a) is the arithmetic average of the absolute values of the surface height deviations, Z_j , measured from the mean plane within the cursor box. Maximum height roughness (R_{max}) is the difference in height between the highest and lowest points on the cross-sectional profile relative to the center line over the length of the profile.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nano-scale polymer surface coating

Here, we describe an inexpensive and applicable process by which a nanometer-scale polymer surface coating layer based on styrene butadiene with varied concentrations, as environmental barrier interphase, was applied to the commercial alkali-resistant glass fibres (ARG) [8]. The as-received (control) and coated fibres, namely C1 and C2, were extracted in a selected highly concentrated alkaline aqueous solution. A detailed statistical description of the fibre tensile strength by either single two-parameter Weibull cumulative distribution function (CDF) or bimodal Weibull CDF [2] is shown in Fig. 1(a). The commercially available alkali-resistant glass fibre shows extensive strength loss after alkali attack. The coated glass fibres have a remarkably higher tensile strength (30%) than the control samples after long-term conditioned in a highly alkaline environment [6].

Fig. 1:

- (a) Comparison of Weibull plots of fracture probability as a function of tensile strength for ARG and C1 fibres before and after extraction in aqueous NaOH solution.
- (b) Comparison of the measured maximum height surface roughness (AFM) with the Griffith strength prediction for both various ARG fibres before and after different surface treatments. Of interest is the tensile strength of the coated fibres remains approximately unchanged after NaOH treatment.

A strong correlation between the tensile strength, roughness and Griffith fracture predictions is noted. We treat the fibre fractures as the result of a competition between failure of external surface, and failure of internal flaws. The variation of the tensile strength with the defect size is shown in the Fig. 1(b), together with the surface maximum roughness, R_{max} results. One interesting observation is that R_{max} followed very closely the line predicted by the Griffith fracture criterion. Moreover, an assessment of changes in the fibre surface chemical and nanomechanical properties is provided. Using nanoindentation, the fibre surface elastic/adhesion properties shift to different direction for the control and coated fibres after alkali environment attack. The surface with styrene-butadiene coating, dominated by acidic groups, is demonstrated that can buffer the alkaline groups of the cementitious matrix and thus avoid damage of the glass fibre itself.

Fibre Surface Mechanical and Chemical Properties

We then in-situ examined the fibre surface elastic properties together with surface chemical characteristics. In these tests nanoindentations were made perpendicularly to the fibre axis and along the fibre diameter line. The curves of indentation force, F , as a function of distance between the tip and the surface can be used to calculate surface stiffness, which records the cantilever Z -displacement, h_{Z-pos} , and deflection, h_{defl} , as the tip approaches/retracts a surface [6]. The contact stiffness, K , is the slope of the initial elastic unloading curve, dF/dh , which includes contributions from both the specimen and the indenter. K is given by

$$K = \frac{dF}{d(h_{Z-pos} - h_{defl})} \quad (1)$$

$$h_{defl} = \frac{F}{k_c} \quad (2)$$

where k_c is the cantilever spring constant. Fig. 2 provides an indication of the variability of the local contact stiffness properties. It can be observed that the stiffness data shift to different

Fig. 2. AFM determination of contact stiffness vs. indentation force for the silicon tip on the surfaces of NEG fibers. Variation of the nanoscale surface properties subjected to alkali attack are indicated by the arrows.

direction for the control and coated fibres after alkali environment attack. Specifically, the stiffness values significantly decrease for the control NEG. This was unexpected, as the apparent contact stiffness should increase when the substrate glass dominates the elastic deformation because of the reduced thickness or totally disappear of the organic sizing layer by the alkalinity. Thus, it suggests that the chemical corrosion causes a reduction of the intrinsic glass surface properties. This is also supported by the aforementioned tensile strength and previous imaging observation of the microrough porous surface without sizing [6]. In sharp contrast, the stiffness value of the styrene-butadiene coated fibres after treatment is slightly higher than the control and original coated specimen. This is clearly attributed to the sizing layer being partly removed (Fig.1(b)) but the intrinsic glass surface properties might be free of corrosion, which is confirmed by the local surface adhesive force measurement

where magnitudes range of the adhesive forces are not greatly influenced by the alkali treatment [11].

We further confirmed the above trends directly through the use of Zetapotential and FTIR-ATR investigations. Zetapotential measurements reveal the electrokinetic potential due to acidic and/or basic groups at a surface layer and allow to predict their interaction with the environment. The control commercial NEG fibre possesses a negative Zetapotential and an isoelectric point (IEP) of about pH 5. This surface is dominated by acidic groups. Due to an additional styrene-butadiene coating (C2) the plateau value and IEP is shifted to more negative values. This is aimed to buffer the alkaline groups of the cementitious matrix and thus avoid damage of the glass fibre itself. By testing both commercial and our coated fibres after alkali treatment a lifetime estimation is aimed. For the control fibre the IEP shifted to a higher pH value and the plateau region disappeared. This behavior was identified earlier for acidic surface layers on E-glass fibres [12] and is in agreement with rest sizings left on the surface interacting with increasing anions concentrations. Interestingly, the acidic groups on the coated fibre's surface still dominate after NaOH treatment indicated by the plateau value and low IEP.

In addition, no hints for sizing on the control specimen after alkali treatment could be found in the ATR-Spectra. It is generally known that the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretch of functional group typically lies around 1720 cm^{-1} while the 1510 cm^{-1} peak is assigned to the para substituted benzene rings found in the commercially available sizing film former backbone [13]. The absorption peaks in the range $3050\text{-}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to the C-H bonds. Very broad bands in the carboxylate region at $\sim 1567\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are probably due to a variety of carbonate species on zirconia. Since on the original fibre a thin sizing was detected, a difference spectra was determined. This difference spectra is equal to the summary of the previously determined spectra of the ethanol and hexane extraction. The chemical corrosion in both polymer sizing and glass surface are primarily responsible for the differences. The coating layer on the fibre contains preferably polystyrene. The spectra before and after alkali treatment for coated fibres are hardly different; two shoulders at 1550 and 1445 that indicate a possible salt formation (carboxylates). Overall, the surface chemical structure information is strongly consistent with the macro- and micro-mechanical characterization. Our data indicated that the coating developed in this study is chemically resistant to the alkali environment.

Composite and Interphase Fracture Performance

We examined the effect of polymer coating on rovings reinforcing actual concrete composites activated by roving pull-out and longitudinal tensile tests (see Fig.3). The clean and smooth topography of the control roving indicates that the filament and cement were physically bonded together before they were separated. The fracture behavior is dominated by the fibres slide each other within the bundle, resulting in quite long pull-out lengths of the fibres (Fig. 3(b)).

On the contrary, the coated fibre bundles with higher coating content (C2) show a significantly higher maximum fracture force, post-debonding friction force and the fracture energy. Proposed explanations for this behavior are integrating of the fibres by coating bridging (particularly for the C2) and the consequent increase in the frictional component of bond or a much less degradation due to limited access of the aggressive solution to the inner part of the rovings. We noted that, from high magnification SEM analysis (Fig. 3(a)) of the interfacial region, a portion of the cement matrix that was bonded on the fibres after pull-out. It indicates that the coating causes both improved corrosion resistance of glass fibre itself and strong interfacial bonding, associated with improved fracture energy absorption capability of its composites.

Fracture in our continuous fibre bundle cement composites consists of fibre bridging zone with fibre bridging and fibre pull-out and a matrix cracking process zone ahead the

macrocrack. Encountered in most continuous fibre cement composites, the dimensions of the bridging zone are comparable to any specimen dimension – a phenomenon known as large scale bridging [14]. Assuming the bridging stress builds up in the bridging zone with length, l_c , the individual fibre in fibre bundle breaks at its weakest point within this region. Practically, l_c can be approximately represented by the maximum length of the fracture fibres after the separation of the opposite sides of the macrocrack of the composites. The total energy absorption mechanisms during the composite fracture process should contribute from the coexistence work of deformation and generation of new surfaces, successive fracture of the fibres (Fig. 3(b)), interfacial debonding/friction associated with fibre pull-out, stress redistribution and so forth. Here, U_i is regarded as the sum of the specific energies absorbed in elastic deformation of the specimen in initial stage, interfacial debonding and stress redistribution. U_F and U_f are energies for successive fracture of fibres and friction during fibre pull-out, respectively. We consider that the embedded roving consist of total number of fibres N and broken fibres n . The main work done, E , and the total load of the fibres, F , which is equally contributed from the summation of individual unbroken fibres, F_j , therefore, can be described by the following formulae:

$$E \approx U_i + U_F + U_f \quad (3)$$

$$F = \frac{\partial U_F}{\partial l} = \sum_{j=1}^{N-n} F_j = \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right) \cdot \frac{E \delta T}{\rho l_c} \quad (4)$$

where E , ρ , T and δ are fiber Young's modulus, density, roving fineness (the weight in grams of 1000 linear meters) and tensile displacement, respectively. We assume that no interaction occurs between the fiber fracture and each individual fiber has the same probability of fracture. Thus, the aforementioned weakest link approach based on the single Weibull distribution function can be used to describe the measured force-displacement curves (Fig. 4) which are normalized by consideration of one roving embedded in cement. By combining Eq. (4) with the single modal Weibull distribution function

$$P = \frac{n}{N+1} = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{s_0}\right)^{m_0}\right] \quad (5)$$

and taking into account $N \approx N+1$ since the roving consists of 1600 filaments, the load-displacement curve of the composite after cement break can be rewritten as a linear function. The simulated force-displacement curves together with the experimental values from both

Fig. 3. Average force-displacement curves of (a) roving pull-out tests and (b) composite tensile tests with control NEG and coated C1 and C2 fibers. The insert pictures show (a) the pulled out fibers (b) fiber fracture/pull-out in the concrete broken during tensile test.

composite tensile and roving pull-out tests, indicate the intrinsic mechanisms involved (Fig. 4). At the first stage of tensile test, the cement matrix breaks first at a high load and the crack propagating in the matrix is halted by the stiff fiber, since the maximum fracture strain of fiber is greater than that of the cement. Simultaneously, the elastic stress is redistributed and the interfacial debonding extends some distance along the fiber bundle with further increase in the external load. The roving pull-out test shows similar behavior of this stage. Then, at the second stage, the successive fracture of the fibers is the dominant behavior. The coated fibre bundles show a significantly higher maximum fracture force, post-debonding friction force and the fracture energy than the control systems. Further insight can be obtained from the fractographic observation by AFM on the nanometer scale. Our recent work suggests that the fractal geometry of fracture surfaces [8] could be linked to the interphase micro-mechanical properties. The nanostructure near the fibre appears to be a key region to be optimised. Overall, the coating causes both improved corrosion resistance of glass fibre itself and strong interfacial bonding, associated with improved fracture toughness of its composites.

Fig. 4: Force-displacement curves of composite tensile and roving pull-out tests for specimen with C1 rovings. Also shown are best-fit curves based on the parameters drawn from the linear log-log regression plots based on the weakest link approach (insert picture). The grey line associated with friction behaviour at the final stage is approximately represented by the difference between the experimental and theoretical (fibre successive fracture) values.

Development of sizings for ARG/ durability/ adhesion Strength

We further developed sizings for ARG made in this Institute (IPF-1, 2,3,4) adjusted to the interaction with a cementitious matrix and adapted for high durability in alkaline environment, based on the research experience of E-glass for tailor-made adhesion strength and compatibility with various polymer matrices. The sizings in combination with polymer coatings show increase of both roving strengths and fracture behaviour of concrete specimens in the longitudinal tensile test at tailor-made formulations. For the development of sizings, special consideration was laid to realize significantly different surface roughness because of its strong influence on the glass fibre strength was already known by previous research [6]. Figure 5 shows, exemplarily, the systematic variation of the roughness of the filament surface by suitable sizings, that is associated with the adhesion/friction in the cementitious matrix. Decreasing roughness (IPF-3 > IPF-4 > IPF-2 > IPF-1) lead to an increase of the roving strength. The sizing IPF-2 is characterized by a very good alkaline resistance [15]. The sizings 1 and 2, in combination with the coatings P1 and P2 achieve very high fracture energies in the longitudinal tensile test of composites. It appears by Table 1 that IPF-1 compared to NEG

nearly has the doubled adhesion strength. The P1 coating, if applied on the sizing, interacts with the cementitious matrix and this leads to comparable values to the equally prepared NEG-ARG. An improved adhesion strength was determined for coating P2. This enhancement of the adhesion strength is in good agreement with the enhanced fracture energy (maximum force) of the longitudinal tensile test of composites.

Table 1: Local adhesion strength τ_d and frictional stress τ_f , obtained from single fibre pull-out tests, roving tensile strength and maximum force from concrete specimen testing

AR-Glas	τ_d , MPa	τ_f , MPa	Roving tensile strength [MPa]	Maximum force (apparent fracture energy) [kN]
NEG 620-01	55.5	2.8	1351	0.3
NEG 620-01/2	91.8	0.2	1367	0.4
IPF-1	108.9	3.1	686	0.4
IPF-1/P1	95.4	3.2	1054	0.7
IPF-1/P2	130.0	5.2	942	0.8

Fig. 5. AFM topography images (Tapping Mode) of selected IPF-ARG surfaces

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